

WATER ABSORPTION AND WATER RESISTANCE OF WATERPROOFING MATERIAL WATERPROOFING-K

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Abstract. *Waterproofing material Waterproofing-K is tested according to two requirements of the standard: water absorption and water resistance of the material. A graph of water absorption of samples of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K with a thickness of 3mm, 5mm and 10mm is constructed. It was proved that the water absorption index of a sample of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K with a thickness of 5mm was the best than the other samples and amounted to 0.59%. According to Gost 8625-77, it was revealed that based on the results obtained from the waterproofness test of the samples of the waterproofing material Waterproofing-K on the surface of three samples there are no traces of water.*

Keywords: *petroleum sludge, gossypole resin, technical sulfur, quicklime, waterproofing material, water absorption, water resistance.*

Introduction. In the world, one of the most common and aggressive factors affecting all construction structures is water. This leads to reduce the strength properties of most building materials, the development of corrosion processes in metal and concrete, rotting wood, the appearance of cracks, mold and moisture, and the destruction of protective layers of structures. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure waterproofing, that is, to protect structures during construction [1].

There are other measures that help to quickly remove water or protect it from penetration, for example, much attention is paid to such works as grinding the surface of parts of construction structures, polishing, forming a protective layer [2-4].

To date, the quality indicators of waterproofing materials depend on the composition of the substrate. The base of the material plays an important role and it is, of course, building bitumen. Bitumen of the BN 90/10 construction grade and its compositions are used as a waterproofing coating. To obtain a high-quality waterproofing material, Waterproofing-K, we have developed a new composite construction bitumen BN 90/10 + 4K based on oil sludge, gossypol resin, technical sulfur and quicklime. Based on the new composition of the construction BN 90/10+4 K bitumen composite, the waterproofing material Waterproofing-K was obtained and tested according to the following methods [5-7].

Research methods. **Water absorption.** The test is carried out on three samples with dimensions $(100 \pm 1) \times (100 \pm 1)$ mm. The prepared sample is weighed (m), then immersed for 1 min in a vessel with water at a temperature of (293 ± 2) K / (20 ± 2) ° C. After that, it is removed from the water, wiped with a cotton cloth or filter paper for 30-60 seconds and weighed (m). Then the sample is again placed in water, the temperature of which is (293 ± 2) K / (20 ± 2) ° C, so that the water layer above it is at least 50 mm, and are maintained for the time specified in the standards

or specifications for a specific material. After that, the sample is removed from the water, drained and weighed again (m) [8].

Water resistance. The test is carried out on three samples with dimensions $(150 \pm 1) \times (150 \pm 1)$ mm using a device equipped with a pressure gauge according to GOST 8625-77 and providing the creation of excessive hydrostatic pressure up to 0.3 MPa [9].

The results of the study. Water absorption. The water absorption of the waterproofing material Waterproofing-K is calculated according to the formula with an accuracy of 0.1 percent:

$$w = \frac{m_3 - m_2}{m_1} \cdot 100\%$$

where, m_3 – the mass of the sample after the test time in water, g;

m_2 – the mass of the sample after a minute test in water, g;

m_1 – weight of the dry sample, g.

The results of the arithmetic mean values of water absorption values are included in Table-1.

Table 1

The results of testing samples of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K

The name of the indicator	Prototypes of Waterproofing-K			Requirements for waterproofing material	
	1-sample thickness of 3mm	2- sample thickness of 5mm	3- sample thickness of 10 mm	Hydrosteclouis ol TU 400-1-51-83	Filizol TU 400-1-409-5-92
1	2	3	4	6	7
Water absorption (w), % by weight:	0,69	0,59	0,66	≤ 1	≤ 1
m_1 - weight of the dry sample, g	310,09	410,08	810,11		
m_2 – the mass of the sample after a minute test in water, g;	311,12	412,39	812,84		
m_3 – the mass of the sample after the test time in water, g;	313,26	414,79	818,21		

The indicators of the samples included in Table 1, which were obtained in the petrochemical laboratory and calculated using the formula of water absorption of samples with a thickness of 3 mm, 5 mm and 10 mm:

1. The thickness of the sample of 3 mm:

$$w = \frac{m_3 - m_2}{m_1} \cdot 100\% = \frac{313,26 - 311,12}{310,09} \cdot 100 = 0,69\%$$

2. The thickness of the sample of 5 mm:

$$w = \frac{m_3 - m_2}{m_1} \cdot 100\% = \frac{414,79 - 412,39}{410,08} \cdot 100 = 0,59\%$$

3. The thickness of the sample of 10 mm:

$$w = \frac{m_3 - m_2}{m_1} \cdot 100\% = \frac{818,21 - 812,84}{810,11} \cdot 100 = 0,66\%$$

Based on the indicators of the samples listed in Table 1, a graph of water absorption of samples of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K is constructed in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Water absorption of samples of waterproofing material Waterproofing-Ks with a thickness of 3mm, 5mm and 10mm

In the laboratory of Petrochemistry of the Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 3 samples of waterproofing material were obtained for a laboratory device.

As can be seen from Table 1 and the graph, the water absorption of a sample of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K with a thickness of 3mm is 0.69%. According to the standard requirements for waterproofing materials, water absorption is to be below 1% and this proves that the sample of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K with a thickness of 3mm has a good indicator.

The water absorption index of a sample of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K with a thickness of 5mm is 0.59%. According to the standard requirements for waterproofing materials, as can be seen from Table 1 and the graph, water absorption is also to be below 1% and this proves that a sample of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K with a thickness of 5mm also has a good indicator [10].

The water absorption index of a sample of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K with a thickness of 10mm is 0.66%. According to the standard requirements for waterproofing materials, as can be seen from Table 1 and the graph, water absorption is also to be below 1% and this proves that a sample of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K with a thickness of 10mm also has a good indicator.

However, the water absorption of a sample of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K with a thickness of 5mm is 0.59% and this indicator is the best of the three.

Another of the main requirements for waterproofing materials is water resistance. Below is the data on the waterproofness test of samples of waterproofing material.

Water resistance. If no globules of water appear on the surface of the material at a given pressure at a certain time, the sample will be accepted as tested. The obtained results and data are included in Table 2.

The tests were carried out according to the method above. All three samples were tested in a laboratory instrument under standard conditions such as pressure (0.1±0.01) MPa for (2±0.1) hours.

As can be seen from Table 2, with the standard requirements for waterproofing materials, that is, water resistance at a pressure of (0.1± 0.01) MPa for (2 ± 0.1) hours, traces of water do not appear on the surface of three samples because these samples withstood pressures up to 6 MPa and this proves that all three samples will be the standard for production of the material.

Table 2

Test results of prototypes of waterproofing material Waterproofing-K

The name of the indicator	Prototypes of Waterproofing-K			Requirements for waterproofing material	
	1-sample thickness of 3mm	2-sample thickness of 5mm	3-sample thickness of 10mm	Hydrostecloiso 1 TU 400-1-51-83	Filizol TU 400-1-409-5-92
1	2	3	4	6	7
Water resistance at a pressure of (0.1=0.01) MPa during (2±0,1) hours	There are no traces on top of the news water	There are no traces on top of the news water	There are no traces on top of the news water	At 5kgs/cm2, the excess hydrostatic pressure is not manifested	There are no traces of water on top of the news

Conclusion. Based on the results and analyses obtained, it can be concluded that according to the water absorption test of the waterproofing material, sample No. 2 has the best indicator and is 0.59%, and according to the water resistance test of the waterproofing material, there are no traces of water on the surface of all three samples.

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